

Deliverable 2.2

‘A policy on mainstreaming entrepreneurialism for the EUTOPIA alliance’

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Executive Summary

The EUTOPIA Alliance is a collaboration between ten universities in Belgium, France, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, the UK, Germany, Italy, Portugal and Romania. One of the EU-funded projects under the EUTOPIA umbrella is called TRAIN (Transformation of Research and Innovation). Supported by the Horizon 2020 'Science with and for Society' initiative, the goal of TRAIN is to pool the resources and expertise of the six founding partners in order to develop a common Research and Innovation strategy for the alliance.

The outputs of EUTOPIA-TRAIN primarily fall into three categories:

- Mapping and evaluation reports
- New tools to facilitate collaboration
- New strategic documents or policy recommendations

This report explores current understanding, awareness and interest in 'entrepreneurialism' amongst EUTOPIA's researcher community. It seeks to identify ways to mainstream entrepreneurialism in the mindset of students and researchers.

The report draws some key conclusions:

1. 'Entrepreneurialism' for the alliance should encompass engagement with all non-academic partners, including non-commercial activity such as 'social entrepreneurship' and 'responsible innovation'.
2. Training is an effective tool to develop a 'culture of innovation' on both an institutional and alliance level.
3. Targeted training for researchers at PhD and supervisor/mentor level has potential to strengthen the innovation pipeline and increase university business collaboration.
4. Bespoke training for arts, social sciences and humanities is recommended to unlock potential beyond STEM disciplines.
5. Mainstreaming 'entrepreneurialism' requires institutional and alliance level recognition and reward of innovation activities.
6. Any EUTOPIA Policy on mainstreaming entrepreneurialism will need to encompass training, access to business, reward and recognition and the positioning of Higher Education and Research in the Innovation ecosystem.

The report will be used by the alliance to:

1. Reflect on the value of these pilot initiatives for future implementation.
2. Identify and develop new activities to further understanding around mainstreaming entrepreneurialism.
3. Share findings and best practice with each other and with other European University Alliances (EUAs).
4. Recommend Policy areas to EUTOPIA.
5. Inform and support other areas of the TRAIN and MORE objectives and outputs.

Institutional Abbreviations

CY Cergy Paris Université	CYU
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Göteborgs Universitet	GU
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Univerza v Ljubljani	UL
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Universitat Pompeu Fabra	UPF
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University of Warwick	UoW
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Vrije Universiteit Brussel	VUB
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1. Introduction

The EUTOPIA Alliance is a collaboration between ten universities in Belgium, France, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, the UK, Germany, Italy, Portugal and Romania. One of the EU-funded projects under the EUTOPIA umbrella is called TRAIN (Transformation of Research and Innovation). Supported by the Horizon 2020 ‘Science with and for Society’ initiative, the goal of TRAIN is to pool the resources and expertise of the six founding partners in order to develop our Research and Innovation activities.

This document constitutes the EUTOPIA-TRAIN deliverable 2.2, described in the TRAIN bid as a **policy on mainstreaming entrepreneurialism for the EUTOPIA alliance and recommendations on how other networks of universities could mainstream entrepreneurialism amongst researchers and students** (page. 18).

1.1. Acknowledgements

In addition to the authors credited on the title pages, we wish to acknowledge our other colleagues in TRAIN WP2: Simona Rataj (Univerza v Ljubljani), Camilla Pettersson (Göteborgs universitet), Tuur Roels (Vrije Universiteit Brussel), Ana Sagardoy, Núria Brunet & Guillem Martí Cervera (Universitat Pompeu Fabra) and Pierre Viste (CY Cergy Paris Université). They have all contributed by engaging in discussions about the format and scope of the deliverable and giving feedback on the initial draft. We would also like to thank Sylvie Niessen (CY Cergy Paris Université) as lead for TRAIN WP4 (Human Capital) for her input. Our thanks are also extended to the newer EUTOPIA partners: Babeş-Bolyai University, Ca’ Foscari University of Venice, Technische Universität Dresden and NOVA University Lisbon for their input in TRAIN-WP2.

1.2. Objectives of the deliverable

As outlined in the bid, under Task 2.2 ‘Recommendations on ways to mainstream entrepreneurial mind-set of researchers and students’ (p.15): *‘Universities are important contributors to society’s ability to generate public goods and services and, as such, could seek to maximise their activity in this area. Universities have not always seen themselves as having an interest in the direct exploitation of the research they do – this has been particularly evident where the commercial exploitation of research is concerned. As a result, the promotion of entrepreneurship and exploitation of research has not necessarily been a priority for universities but has been left to individual researchers, research teams, or third parties. Indeed, the definition of what research is capable of translation into societal benefits has often been restricted. The reality is that collaboration between institutions in this area is very clearly the exception rather than the rule. This project aims to identify the steps that EUTOPIA can take to redress this situation.’*

The key purpose of this deliverable is to stimulate a more positive opinion of knowledge and technology transfer and cooperation between business and academia by addressing myths, prejudices and stereotypes and seeking ways to mainstream entrepreneurship in the mindset of

students and researchers. Ultimately, the goal is to increase and improve relations with external organisations (especially regional organisations) in a way that increases and enhances knowledge transfer. A further long-term aim is to make all EUTOPIA regions, and their innovation eco-systems, more accessible to each other, so that good practices can be shared and new opportunities identified. EUTOPIA's approach is grounded in the Knowledge Square model, illustrated in [Deliverable 2.5](#), which shows how education, research, innovation and society intersect and feed into one another.

Scope of the deliverable

Research outputs of EUTOPIA-TRAIN have been impacted by the Covid-19 pandemic which limited mobility opportunities and relationship building capacity. The evidence gathered from pilots tested in this deliverable can only be measured on a short-term basis due to the limited timeframe of the TRAIN project. We recognise that pilot initiatives can take several years to develop impact. Analysis of gradual changes in researcher and institutional behaviour, attitudes and culture over a longer timeframe are not possible in this report. Furthermore, pilot initiatives for innovation rewards and incentives, such as seed funding and EUTOPIA innovation awards, were not foreseen and included in the TRAIN budget. Larger scale initiatives such as these could be explored and tested in EUTOPIA-MORE or future EUTOPIA projects. Institutional self-assessment of the effectiveness of innovation support structures, based on quantitative data (e.g. number of patents) has been conducted by TRAIN-WP5 through [Deliverable 5.1](#) (Report on the future role of GLENN office). While this data is valuable, D2.2 is primarily concerned with measuring awareness, understanding and effectiveness through a more qualitative, consultative approach with key stakeholders. Self-selecting sampling by WP2 members means that the majority of PhD students and researchers consulted for this deliverable already have some awareness of innovation and EUTOPIA. Further stakeholder engagement could attempt to target PhD students and researchers who are not involved in innovative activities or EUTOPIA to further understand the barriers and motivators to engagement. Finally, it is important to note that although new EUTOPIA partners have been consulted, the findings included in this deliverable are based on research carried out by the original six EUTOPIA-TRAIN partners (not the full ten).

1.3. Definition of entrepreneurialism

A key challenge (and strength) of working as an alliance of ten different institutions, located in different countries, is the variation of language relating to 'entrepreneurialism'. Each geographic partner has a different interpretation and expectation of what we mean by 'entrepreneurialism'. Therefore, it is important to clarify EUTOPIA-TRAIN's definition. While many Technology Transfer Officers (TTOs) are traditionally commercially driven there has also been an increased focus on promoting societal impact or 'social entrepreneurship' in recent years. The 'Planetary Wellbeing' initiative at UPF, for example, facilitates the development of innovation projects towards non-commercial outcomes. Similarly, in Sweden, the Professors' privilege (the right for academics to fully own the IP of their research) means that there is subsequently less drive, in universities, towards 'commercialisation' and more focus on 'societal impact'. The rationale behind this is that since the researcher gets to decide how and to what aim to exploit their research results, that aim often lies closer to 'societal impact' than it does for some Tech Transfer Offices (TTOs), which are more commercially driven. These ambitions often end up coinciding in any modern venture anyway, as all

three pillars of sustainability; social, environmental and economic, including a viable financial model for continued implementation, are important factors for any new solutions - but it's important to understand the main driving force and starting point for valorisation in the target group for new initiatives. Thus, it is even more pronounced in Sweden, but still relevant for all universities who need the researcher on board when developing their idea, to align with the researcher's own aim. In UK universities, although overlapping, 'impact' and 'innovation' are commonly separated out into different streams and funding mechanisms due to the way that research is accessed at a national level through the Research Excellence Framework (REF). For the purposes of this deliverable and other TRAIN-WP2 outputs, the definition of 'entrepreneurialism' or 'innovation' will mean, in the broadest sense, the implementation of academic knowledge and knowledge-based assets and solutions outside of academia; not only technical products, but also other results of research, including social sciences, humanities and arts – and not only through commercialisation, but also through other pathways to impact, e.g. various forms of transfer to and collaboration with societal organisations. While the definition offered here accounts for diversity in language, it also acknowledges that these activities are all interconnected and part of the job of a complete academic environment or a connected community. Crucially, this recognises that starting a collaboration as a pathway to impact may turn into a commercialisation opportunity or vice versa.

1.4. Definition of student

Following a planning workshop which took place in March 2022, TRAIN-WP2 members completed a short questionnaire to help focus thinking about who we could engage with. The outcomes of that questionnaire indicated that TRAIN-WP2 could engage exclusively with PhD students rather than undergraduate or postgraduate students. The rationale behind this decision is that TTOs usually offer support to commercialise *research* results rather than entrepreneurial ideas without any research behind them. Therefore, as PhD students are integrated in the research structures and are also the profiles mainly involved in new business creation, we made this selection. Furthermore, many TTOs do not work directly with undergraduate or postgraduate students because there are other services that are tailored to their needs (i.e. Warwick Enterprise, Ljubljana University Incubator). This distinction will ensure consistent and useful feedback with a clearly defined group. In addition, WP2 deliverables feed into the work carried out in other WPs, particularly WP4 which has a sole focus on PhD students. Therefore, for the purposes of all TRAIN-WP2 deliverables, 'student' will refer to PhD students as our target student engagement group. However, we will also reflect on the current provision of training across the range of undergraduate and postgraduate students through desk-based research and discussions with PhD students about their past experiences at bachelor and master level.

2. Consultations

An in-depth desk-based analysis of [current innovation-related provision](#) at EUTOPIA partners was conducted at the start of the project. Building on initial consultations with researchers undertaken as part of [Deliverable 2.4](#) (A database containing EUTOPIA external partners and researchers) additional consultations were carried out with PhD students to gauge current understanding, awareness and experience of innovation in their institutions.

2.1. Methodology

An online [questionnaire](#) was designed and used to collect data from PhD students (see appendix 1). WP2 partners adopted different approaches to data gathering, producing a varied set of responses. Some partners conducted semi-structured interviews in person or online with a targeted group of PhD students while others distributed the questionnaire more broadly, asking PhD students to complete the survey themselves. PhD students at all stages of their research and from a range of different disciplines were asked to take part in the survey. In general, PhD students were enthusiastic and willing to take part in the questionnaire. However, limited time impacted availability and uptake. Additionally, some PhD students work remotely which meant that in person interviews were less practical. A total of 57 responses were collected across the alliance. Due to the limited sample size and varying nature of the way that data was collected we have primarily focussed on qualitative analysis of the data. At the end of the survey, respondents were asked if they would be interested in participating in a follow-on focus group meeting or workshop with 59% agreeing to be involved in future activity.

2.2. Gender balance

A question about gender was included in the questionnaire to ensure gender balance in this research. It is worth noting that in some cases a single response was submitted by multiple people and in others a single person submitted multiple responses. Out of those PhD students who responded, 48% were female and 50% were male (2% preferred not to say).

2.3. Analysis

Interest in and understanding of innovation

The level of interest in innovation amongst PhD students interviewed is high, with only 2% of respondents indicating that they are not interested. PhD students were asked what innovation means to them, producing a range of responses including (but not limited to): ‘thinking outside the box’, ‘finding new ways to solve old problems’, ‘development of new products’. Fuller descriptions of innovation included: ‘improvements in all fields of society’ and ‘introducing new technologies and practices that will improve lives of people and not long or short term negatively impact the

environment'. For most PhD students, in line with EUTOPIA-TRAIN's own definition, innovation encompasses a broad range of activities that relate to societal impact.

Awareness and uptake of innovation training

Around half of respondents were not aware of any opportunities to learn about innovation and entrepreneurship within their institution and only 16% of students interviewed have undertaken any relevant such training during their PhD. Similarly, only 25% of students interviewed have undertaken training related to innovation and entrepreneurship at bachelor or masters level. Most students reported not having time to engage with training in this area. Furthermore, access and availability to relevant training was identified as another key barrier. Students were asked to elaborate further on why they haven't carried out innovation training, prompting some interesting responses: 'training has been more research focussed', 'there were no opportunities in my field', 'I would have applied to more courses if they were online', 'within my work field it is frowned upon to focus on commercialisation and entrepreneurship'.

Awareness and effectiveness of innovation support structures

63% of respondents reported that they are not aware of innovation support structures within their institutions (e.g. tech transfer offices, business developers, business office etc.) and only 13% have accessed these services. The majority of respondents cited 'not had an idea that I wanted to pursue' and 'there was no need' as the main reasons why they have not accessed these services. This was followed by 'time', 'availability' and 'interest'. Some valuable insights were captured in the 'other' category with respondents reporting that they 'hadn't considered that you can be both as the same'. In particular, one respondent stated that they were: 'not aware that it could be an opportunity. My supervisors collaborated with Tech Transfer before and did not propose it to use it for my research'.

Awareness and uptake of mobility opportunities

73% of students surveyed are aware of mobility opportunities at their institutions and just under half have participated in mobility opportunities, with the majority citing Erasmus+ and EUTOPIA cotutelle programmes. The majority of students reported positively that mobility helped to develop innovation skills. Respondents elaborated, stating: 'it is useful to experience two different university mindsets', 'having two different supervisors at Warwick and Ljubljana has helped me to have multiple points of view' and 'helped me open my mind to interdisciplinary thinking, that could eventually lead to innovation'.

Digital solutions to innovation

Building on findings in [Deliverable 4.4](#) (Report on digital collaboration solutions) which highlights the necessity of digital tools to facilitate collaborative research, participants were asked about their experience of using digital solutions for innovation. 56% of respondents said that they have explored 'virtual meeting platforms' such as Zoom, Google Meet and Microsoft Teams which are now common practice in a post-pandemic world. Only a small number have explored 'blended networking' and

‘virtual mobility’. The benefits of using digital meeting platforms include reduced costs, ability to connect with people in different geographical locations and increased accessibility to virtual events/conferences. Other tools used by participants include Padlet and Slack (to share ideas) and LinkedIn and ResearchGate (for networking). When asked why they had not explored digital solutions responses included: ‘Never related to innovation, just in general the past 2 years’ ‘not for innovation itself, but more every day work’ and ‘don’t know what the other options are’. The survey responses indicate that more can be done to raise awareness and understanding amongst EUTOPIA researchers of potential digital solutions to innovation beyond the commonplace tools outlined above. The University of Warwick has recently piloted [My Innovation Collective](#), a free peer network to help businesses solve problems and accelerate innovation. My innovation Collective functions on the foundation of skills exchange and time-banking. It connects those that have skills and experience to register as mentors and pledge hours in support of new local start-ups or existing businesses ambitious to grow. Digital tools such as these can be introduced and utilized on a EUTOPIA wide level. Furthermore, the emergence of new AI technologies such as [Chat GPT](#) could be considered in terms of practicing responsible innovation.

Incentives and rewards structures for innovative activity

When asked whether there are clear incentives and reward structures within their institution for engaging in innovative activity, around half of the PhD students interviewed did not know (22% said responded ‘yes’ and 30% said ‘no’). When asked whether a reward structure would motivate them to further engage in innovative activity, 45% said ‘yes’ and 37% said ‘maybe’. Respondents were asked about what kinds of rewards and incentives might motivate them further and responses included (but were not limited to): ‘funding, time (ideally hours)’, ‘specific time to work on innovation’, ‘career and acknowledgements’, ‘scholarships, free courses, online courses’. Whilst some were motivated by financial rewards, others stated that they were ‘not motivated by financial rewards as not in academic for money!’. Innovation rewards and incentives are examined in more detail in section 4 of this deliverable.

3. Training pilots

TRAIN-WP2 developed a series of innovation training models for PhD students and researchers, based on findings from the consultations outlined in Section 2. These pilots also draw on recommendations from reports produced by other TRAIN WPs including [Deliverable 5.1](#) (Report on the future role of GLENN office) which highlights that entrepreneurship support and awareness could be improved by fostering new activities and training among both researchers and students. Training surveys conducted by WP4 also indicate the need for additional support on entrepreneurship and innovation awareness. Participants were asked to provide feedback by completing a short questionnaire before and after the training to gauge impact and effectiveness of these pilots. All trainings were offered internationally (language: English) to foster knowledge transfer.

3.1. 'Introduction to Innovation' workshop

Rationale

73% of PhD students consulted across the alliance are interested in 'innovation'. However, the majority have not undertaken any training related to innovation or entrepreneurship during their PhD. This is due to multiple reasons including access, availability, time and interest. A short, general 'introduction to innovation' was piloted on a EUTOPIA level.

Format

Two-hour online interactive workshop led by a tech transfer expert, aimed at PhD students providing an introduction to the concept of innovation and asking the participants to consider what innovation means, why it is important and how it could relate to their own research and impact.

Figure 1. 'What is Innovation?' slide showing the Innovation Wheel

Outcomes

Participants were asked how 'innovative' (creative or entrepreneurial) they consider themselves to be before and after the workshop. Individual definitions of 'innovation' varied but it was generally defined by the group as 'producing new knowledge' or 'creating new products or process'. On average, participants rated their level of innovation (according to this definition) as 6.4 (1 = not very, 10 = very) in the pre-workshop survey; with this number increasing to 7.9 after the workshop indicating a slight shift in perception. 43% of respondents to the post-workshop survey said that it made them more confident and aware about what 'innovation' means and how innovation relates to their research. **Crucially, 86% of respondents said that they are now more likely to explore and undertake additional innovation training opportunities and 57% said that they would seek help from the innovation support team at their institution if they had an innovative idea.** Respondents unanimously agreed that the length of the workshop (2 hours) was 'about right' and 86% of those surveyed said that the length of the workshop was a contributory factor in signing up. Interestingly, several students requested a 'certificate of attendance' after this workshop. One PhD student explained that this was required by their institution as 'proof of attendance' instead of being at work. This indicates that, at least for some students, training opportunities such as these, that are not directly related to 'research', may be difficult to access and justify to their supervisors/mentors.

3.2. 'Innovation in Social Sciences, Arts and Humanities research' workshop

Rationale

According to the [2021 ASPECT \(A SHAPE Platform for Entrepreneurship, Commercialisation and Transformation\) report](#), HEIs are not equipped to accommodate social sciences research commercialisation and there is a lack of 'business skills' amongst social sciences researchers (p. 26). 60% of students interviewed by TRAIN-WP2 have not engaged with business or industry and 87% of students have not accessed innovation support structures, predominantly because they have not had an idea that they wanted to pursue. PhD students in social science, arts and humanities subjects were particularly unsure how their research connected with entrepreneurship and felt that innovation training tends to be geared towards STEM subjects. A 'myth busting' training session may empower researchers in these disciplines to reframe their research through an innovative lens and explore commercial potential.

Format

A half-day online workshop to introduce PhD students and researchers, from relevant disciplines, to the fundamentals of research commercialisation in the social sciences and arts, build awareness and capacity, highlight resources and platforms, and help build a collaborative network to share best practice. Students were asked to complete a questionnaire before and after the session to gauge impact, gather feedback and capture potential shifts in mindset.

**INNOVATION – COMMERCIALIZATION:
WHAT CAN WE COMMERCIALISE FROM SOCIAL SCIENCE, ARTS AND HUMANITIES RESEARCH?**

KNOW-HOW (E.G
CONSULTANCY,
LICENSING)

COPYRIGHT (E.G
METHODS, TOOLS,
SOFTWARE, IMAGES
AND OTHER VISUAL
MEDIA, WRITTEN
TEXT)

DATABASE RIGHTS
(EVEN A
SPREADSHEET)

PATENTS (E.G NOVEL
BUSINESS PROCESSES)

Commercialisation is the process of turning an idea into commercial products or services. This could involve delivering consultancy, licencing of IP (i.e. the items above) to a third party such as a company, or it could involve setting up an entirely separate enterprise.

Figure 2. Slide from 'Innovation in social sciences, arts and humanities research' workshop

Outcomes

The majority of participants who responded to the pre-workshop questionnaire had little or no previous experience of research innovation and commercialisation. When asked what they would like to know, responses ranged from: 'I'd like to know, how innovation in arts, humanities and social sciences research is distinct from STEM innovation and commercialisation' to 'What is commercialisation and how does it apply to social sciences? We rarely sell products or seek to translate our ideas into commercial avenues. Isn't the contribution of higher education to society something more important than commercial profit and turning our research into products?' The second response captures a deeply ingrained mentality towards 'entrepreneurialism' based on the philosophical premise that research could not be translated into commercial profit.

Respondents to the post-workshop questionnaire felt that they now knew more about commercialisation of social sciences, arts and humanities research and were 'likely' to apply learning from the workshop. All respondents felt that the workshop highlighted recourses and platforms for commercialisation of social sciences, arts and humanities that they were previously unaware of. When asked what actions they would take based on the learning from the workshop, responses included: 'Re-think my research and see the gaps missing to bridge contents', 'I will complete the Impact Gap Canvas', 'I will collaborate more with colleagues from different disciplines to discuss innovative research possibilities'.

3.3. 'Innovative PhDs workshop'

Rationale

Almost half of the PhD students consulted were not aware of opportunities to learn about innovation and entrepreneurship at their institutions. Training undertaken tends to be focussed on research development and other skills development. Students interviewed were unsure how innovation fits into their future goals and haven't considered the possibility of pursuing both simultaneously. This workshop addressed the role that PhD programmes can play in instilling an entrepreneurial mindset in postgraduate students.

Format

One hour and a half online workshop led by an external consultant aimed at innovation support staff and researchers, in all disciplines, across the EUTOPIA alliance who are current or future PhD supervisors/mentors. This workshop facilitated discussion about how institutions can create a culture of innovation and look closely at the role of supervisors/mentors in empowering PhD students to explore innovation *alongside* their degree.

Exercise: How does innovation relate to your research area?

- How does innovation relate to your research?
- Maybe there are different application areas?
- Are there alternative approaches to solve the same problem?
- How might an innovative way of thinking open new possibilities?

Figure 3. Slide from the 'Innovative PhDs' workshop

Outcomes

Supervisors/mentors who participated in the workshop were asked to complete a post-workshop questionnaire. 83% of respondents said that, as a result of the workshop, they now have more understanding and awareness of how innovation can be explored alongside a PhD. 67% of those who responded said they currently already hold conversations about innovation with their students at the beginning of their PhD, but 83% of the respondents said that, as a result of the workshop, they are even more likely to have a conversation about innovation with their PhD students.

3.4. 'Sustainability Training School'

Rationale

EUTOPIA-2050 coordinated a successful student focussed 'EUTOPIA Innovation Conference' in July 2022 on the theme of 'European Universities and Sustainable Development'. Undergraduate and postgraduate students were asked to consider why innovation is important in relation to sustainability. Building on this initiative, TRAIN-WP2 piloted a '[Sustainability Training School](#)' (STS) for Early Career Researchers in conjunction with the University of Warwick's [Institute for Global Sustainable Development](#). The pilot STS aimed to support skills development, including innovation, and ideas exchange on the theme of 'Resilience and Sustainable Development'. The rationale for this activity is rooted in exploring how innovation and impact could be integrated into training programmes and models for multidisciplinary and cross-cultural research and in response to global challenges.

Figure 4. Screen shot of Sustainability Training School webpage

Format

One-week training school centred around skills development, including a two-hour session entitled 'Becoming Innovators: Design Thinking and Innovation in Your Research'. Throughout the week long programme, participants co-produced knowledge relevant to current global challenges, developed their professional skills, and expanded their international networks. Participants are requested to maintain an ongoing participation in this network and may be requested to provide nominal ambassadorial duties and feedback for the development of future training schools.

Figure 5. Slide from ‘Becoming innovators’ workshop showing the ‘Stages of Design Thinking’

Figure 6. Slide from ‘Becoming innovators’ workshop showing Innovator’s DNA – IGSD edition

Outcomes

Participants from 26 countries, of different age, religion, philosophy attended the STS including representatives from EUTOPIA’s global partners Kyungpook National University (South Korea) and Monash University (Australia). Participants shared their individual research, with in-depth feedback, and learned to work together through team-building skills and group projects. They were exposed to innovative methods, public and policy engagement; sustainability trails, and engagement with

sustainability champions and strategic partner-networks. All participants were asked to complete a short questionnaire after the training programme was completed. Initial feedback indicates that this initiative provided participants with the opportunity to work across different disciplines and cultures to identify **challenge-led innovation** and **impact pipelines**. One participant reflected that ‘entire programme has provided me with a different lens to look at my Supply Chain Resilience which I would like to explore if allowed by my supervisors’. Another participant reported that ‘seeing my research from different angles was eye-opening’ and concluded that they ‘learned a lot that will help me re-think my research design, methodologies, and impact’.

3.5. Innovation training for Science and Innovation Fellows (SIFs)

Rationale

In addition to the training pilots outlined above, developed through consultations with researchers and PhD students, WP2 also drew on training activities organised by other WPs. TRAIN-WP4 coordinated an innovation and impact training session for EUTOPIA SIFs (fellows at post doc level) in conjunction with WP2 members. As part of WP2’s work relating to D2.2, participants were therefore asked to complete a pre- and post-training questionnaire to assess effectiveness and evaluate the potential for future implementation.

Figure 7. ‘Innovation and Impact’ workshop slide for SIFs

Format

A one-day in person training workshop delivered by TTO/Innovation office staff from University of Gothenburg, University of Warwick and University of Ljubljana. The session contained theory, practical exercises where participants practised formulating a value proposition and an impact plan

based on their own research, discussions and case studies from EUTOPIA universities. The content focussed on what 'impact' is and why it is important, how to plan impact and navigate impact with intellectual property. The session also highlighted the innovation support available in EUTOPIA.

Outcomes

Responses to the post workshop questionnaire indicate that most participants had a better understanding of 'innovation' and 'impact' after completing the training session. Several participants reported that the training was too focussed on commercialisation and STEM-research results and expressed a desire for more specific training relating to the humanities, arts and social sciences. Participants would value more concrete examples from these disciplines including 'a researcher who has been through the process and can articulate the most effective ways to be impactful'. In addition, participants requested more group work and more interaction. Participants were also asked what support they would need to facilitate more impact in their research. Responses included (but were not limited to) 'networking', 'partnership with stakeholders' and 'funding for dissemination activities', however many also said that they didn't know yet, relying on their institution's impact/innovation team to make the first move.

3.6. Impact training for Young Leaders Academy (YLA)

Rationale

EUTOPIA-TRAIN WP4 coordinated an impact training session for EUTOPIA YLAs in conjunction with WP2. Research England's definition of 'impact' for the Research Excellence Framework (REF) is 'the effect on, change or benefit to the economy, society, culture, public policy or services, health, the environment or quality of life, beyond academia'. As part of WP2's work relating to this deliverable, participants were also asked to complete a pre- and post-training questionnaire to gauge the effectiveness of this model for future implementation.

Format

A one-day interactive online training workshop led by Impact Managers at the University of Warwick with input from two researchers as guest speakers. The first session was structured around what 'impact' is, why it is important and how to get started including the 'seven steps' of impact, identifying stakeholders and working with policymakers. The second part of the workshop explored how impact is measured and evaluated including the 'Theory of Change' model and evidence gathering. Participants were asked to apply learning by designing their own impact strategy during the workshop.

Figure 8. Slide from ‘Introduction to Impact’ YLA workshop

Outcomes

Although based on a small number of respondents, the post-workshop data indicates that, overall, participants’ understanding of impact increased. After the workshop, participants were more likely to think about non-academic stakeholders for their research and felt more confident in measuring impact and formulating an impact plan for their research.

4. Innovation rewards and incentives

TRAIN WP2 conducted two pilot focus group meetings with key stakeholders to further understanding of rewards and incentives for PhD students and researchers to engage with innovation. The focus group meetings were split into ‘implementers’ (i.e. colleagues who have been involved in implementing an innovative reward or incentive) and ‘recipients’ (i.e. researchers who have received or benefited from an innovation reward or incentive).

Rationale

As outlined in Section 2.3, around half of the PhD students consulted are not aware of rewards and incentives within their institutions for engaging in innovative activity. PhD students interviewed reported positively that a reward structure would motivate them to further engage in innovative activity, therefore it is important to explore this topic further with the ultimate goal of mainstreaming entrepreneurialism.

There is increasing demand on academia to contribute to the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals and the overall impact in society. Increasingly, universities are being seen as a source of talent, entrepreneurship, future-oriented innovation, and a lead player in collaborations for regional development. There are many researchers who are driven by societal challenges, local as well as global, that feel a social responsibility and want to contribute to solving these issues. However, the threshold to do so is high for many researchers and the system often seems to contain more barriers than incentives to overcome them. There is a perception that one gets little or no acknowledgement and reward for putting time and effort into collaboration, innovation, value creation and utilization activities.

Many academics struggle to balance the often-contradictory expectations placed upon them when navigating the political demands of joining forces to resolve societal issues versus academic values of academic freedom and autonomy, and while incentive systems and funding schemes are still almost purely excellence-driven. One main reason why many researchers still see mainly hindrances, even risks, with spending time on activities other than research, is that researchers are assessed almost entirely based on scientific excellence. This is measured by their track record of publications (including metrics such as citations and journal impact factors) and obtained research grants – and it is true both for recruitment, review and promotion processes, and when being assessed by external research funders. The same is true also for assessing, ranking and allocating of funding to research organisations: the ‘publish or perish’ culture prevails in all of our universities. There is broad agreement among the research community that the research assessment system needs to be updated, and there are major forces at work trying to reform it, on national and international levels. Thus, we hope that the research assessment system of tomorrow will recognise impact-aiming activities and reward contributions to society to a much higher degree than it does today.

EUTOPIA has recently signed up to the [COARA](#) (Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment) agreement signalling a step in the right direction. Furthermore, the development of EUTOPIA’s own Research Assessment Framework (TRAIN WP3) advocates broader recognition of public-private (or other academic-non-academic) collaboration or university spin-offs. Due to the ongoing

international and national processes of reforming research assessment, and the intricacies of each universities' own processes around personnel, it is not within the scope of the EUTOPIA-TRAIN project to suggest and pilot such systematic changes. Instead, the focus will remain on the things that are within our mandate to affect – what types of incentives and rewards could we suggest and pilot from a EUTOPIA level, for all the (now ten) universities in our alliance, that could help lower the threshold for researchers and PhD students to engage in innovation activities?

Methodology

An external facilitator was contracted to advise on and conduct both the focus group meetings. Both meetings were one and a half hours long and took place online with relevant representatives from partner institutions. A set of questions were put together by TRAIN-WP members (see appendix 2). EUTOPIA partners were asked, in advance, to summarise existing and past innovation rewards and incentive initiatives at their institutions.

Existing types of innovation rewards and incentives

Before carrying out the focus group meetings, EUTOPIA partners were asked for a short overview of existing innovation and impact rewards and incentives available at their institutions. Full details of these are stored on the TRAIN SharePoint for reference however, for the purposes of the focus group meetings, these are broadly defined as one of the following 'types' of initiative:

- Proceeds from commercialisation/valorisation activities
- Proof of Concept (PoC) funding for 'commercialisation, innovation, utilisation' projects
- Seed fund for collaboration activities
- Courses
- Incubation including funding (of ventures)
- Support for creative projects
- Regional challenge driven competitions
- Training programmes

'Implementer' focus group meeting

Key themes

A **targeted approach** to communication and engagement is key; innovation is not for everyone, so TTOs need to understand, focus on, reach and cater to those researchers that are 'willing' and 'able'. This approach could not only apply to early career researchers, generally perceived to be more 'open' to innovation, but also apply to more established academics who are willing to engage. It is important for TTOs to work with this '**coalition of the willing**' (those researchers who are already motivated) by getting them to be 'change leaders' at universities to build a culture of innovation.

The development of a culture of innovation requires **institutional level recognition** of innovative activities through senior management (at university, faculty and departmental levels). As an example, at GU, a strategic decision was taken by one department, five years ago, to increase the engagement of researchers in collaboration and innovation through **recruitment** and **salary criteria**, increasing the importance and quality of the collaboration and innovation experience. UL has been

supporting innovative researchers through the Rector's award for best innovation for more than decade. In addition, UL has developed an internal Innovation fund in 2020, dedicated to funding motivated researchers with potential innovations. In 2023 the budget of the fund increased by 30%, as a result of strategic support to innovative researchers. There are plans for further budget increases in place.

'Recipients' focus group meeting

Key themes

Personal contact is important in the dissemination of information about innovation rewards and incentives. Researchers are often oversaturated with information about opportunities (conferences, calls etc.) and receive a large volume of emails from different sources which can end up in a 'mental' spam folder. Conversations with researchers tend to be more effective than email newsletters/updates.

Encouragement from PI or supervisor/mentor to apply for innovation-related awards is an important factor and motivator for early career researchers and PhD students. Participants reported that the barrier for engagement with this group is already generally quite low, therefore encouragement for their PI or supervisor/mentor can be instrumental in developing interest.

Showcasing and celebrating successes of researchers working in the innovation space is important. Making these successes more visible to other researchers has the potential to lower the threshold for engagement and make it feel 'more achievable'.

Departmental acceptance and acknowledgement can make it easier for researchers to participate in innovative activity. Recognition by heads of department that researchers have 'permission' to carry out non-teaching/research related activity is a key factor in removing a barrier to engaging in innovative activity.

Time is a key factor for all participants in terms of what they need in order to engage and keep engaging with innovative activity. A departmental or university level policy indicating what percentage of time a researcher can spend on this type of work may help to mainstream innovative activity.

The risk factor of engaging in innovative activity is not always discussed and could be acknowledged. Researchers need to weigh up rewards versus risk when applying for innovation related grants and funding. If unsuccessful, innovation grants, like research grants, have the potential to jeopardise an academic's position career wise. It is important to foster a 'no fear of failure' culture centred around gaining valuable experience. And for universities to try to mitigate risks related to researchers engaging in both innovation and collaboration in various ways.

Transferable skills are an incentive for researchers to engage with innovation and gain skills which can be applied in alternative career paths. Even after unsuccessful innovation projects, researchers state that they have gained valuable learnings from the experience.

Recognition for end users is a key motivator for researchers to engage with innovation. Participants reported that seeing people/companies using the outputs of their research was a positive affirmation of their activity.

Becoming a role model or mentor for others can also be a rewarding factor and personal driver for some participants.

5. Conclusions

Consultations with PhD students have established that, while interested in innovation, current understanding and awareness of innovation, in this group, is limited and could be expanded. Feedback collected from the pilots undertaken by TRAIN-WP2 evidence the potential for training to help mainstream entrepreneurialism in universities. Limited time plays a key factor in enabling both students and researchers to access innovation training. Short, 'taster' training sessions such as the 'introduction to innovation' pilot could be rolled out on a regular basis for new cohorts of EUTOPIA PhD students to 'plant the seed' early on and encourage researchers to think about how innovation could relate to their research. The scope and focus of the workshop could be broadened to encompass social sciences, arts and humanities disciplines with less focus on 'big business' and more focus on the 'student journey'. Additionally, bespoke, in-depth training on innovation in social sciences, arts and humanities would help to debunk and dismantle the dominant narrative that innovation is predominantly STEM related. Feedback gathered from training pilots indicates that innovation and impact training could be both interactive and include researcher experiences where possible. Training for PhD supervisors and mentors could also help to shift the way that students think about and engage with innovation alongside their degree. For PhD students and younger researchers, the attitude and approach to innovation of their mentor/supervisor plays a great role in whether they will explore innovation as a route within or after their research journey.

Key findings gathered through the focus group meetings on rewards and incentives for engaging with innovation indicate that this is a fruitful area for further investigation. Researchers were keen to engage with this activity, but limited time and availability meant that they were unable to take part. Lack of institutional level recognition for engagement with innovation is a barrier for many researchers who feel that they need time and permission to embark on non-research or teaching related activities. Without a change in top-down approach, institutions (and alliances) will struggle to develop a culture of innovation. Discussions at the [2023 University Industry Innovation Network \(UIIN\) conference](#), where EUTOPIA disseminated findings, concluded that even if innovation is recognised within a HEI, it would need to be recognised across the sector otherwise promotion can only take place within the host institution. [Henley Business School](#) is currently doing [research on embedding entrepreneurship and research commercialisation into academic promotion pathways](#) which could help inform EUTOPIA policies in this area moving forward.

6. Recommendations

The recommendations outlined below are based on research conducted by TRAIN-WP2 through a programme of stakeholder engagement activities over the course of the project. These recommendations feed into both EUTOPIA's Research Assessment Framework (WP3) and EUTOPIA's HR Strategy (WP4), particularly relating to reward and recognition, recruitment and training. While it is not within the scope of EUTOPIA to change institutional level policy, these recommendations form the areas that could be onboarded at an alliance policy level to generate a culture of innovation through a top-down/bottom-up approach. It is envisaged that any policy on mainstreaming entrepreneurialism will include competence development (training), incentives, and external competence and capacity(?) (business/societal impact):

Proposed Policy Statement:

EUTOPIA recognises that to contribute to the economic growth, job creation, societal change and application of research and knowledge across Europe and beyond, it must promote entrepreneurialism in all areas of its ecosystem. A culture of innovation, creativity, and entrepreneurial mindset among students, faculty, and staff is vital, but the additional elements of business, not for profit and government organisations into the ecosystem enables challenge led innovation and application of research.

Through continuous development and evaluation, training programmes will be developed across all areas of PhD, academic, support staff and external businesses to raise awareness and improve the innovation culture.

Incentives and rewards opportunities will be key to embedding the innovation culture throughout the alliance. A structured, equitable, fair and accessible incentives (reward and recognition) structure will continue to be explored and local schemes tested.

Regular activities to engage business and societal organisations will be embedded to enable greater challenge led solution finding.

Training

1. EUTOPIA's definition of 'Entrepreneurialism' or 'Innovation' should encompass engagement with all non-academic partners, including non-commercial activity such as 'social entrepreneurship' and 'responsible innovation'.
2. Define an 'innovation' scope framework for trainings, to pedagogically show which topic areas are relevant for researchers, students and HEI staff, ultimately also in various phases of their 'innovation maturity', and when possible integrate it into researcher career development frameworks being implemented.
3. Develop and deliver innovation training on an alliance level to generate a common 'culture of innovation'.
4. Develop and deliver targeted training for researchers at PhD and supervisor/mentor level.
5. Develop and deliver bespoke innovation/impact training for arts, social sciences and humanities to unlock potential engagement beyond STEM disciplines.

6. Design innovation/impact training that is interactive and includes ‘first-hand’ researcher experience.
7. Develop a suite of bite sized (1–2 hour sessions) for online attendance in groups, or to dip into when time allows.

Rewards and Incentives

1. Coordinate additional focus group meetings on rewards and incentives and extend to two hours. Integrate this work with institutional, national and international initiatives for incentive system development.
2. Develop and pilot alliance level recognition and reward mechanisms for innovative activity e.g., a ‘EUTOPIA Innovation Awards’ scheme (subject to funding availability).
3. Concretely integrate and nurture ‘innovation’, as a part of the knowledge square model, into complete academic environments and connected communities.

7. Appendix 1: PhD student questionnaire

EUTOPIA-TRAIN PhD student questionnaire

The EUTOPIA Alliance is a collaboration between ten universities in Belgium, France, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, the UK, Germany, Italy, Portugal and Romania. One of the EU-funded projects under the EUTOPIA umbrella is called TRAIN (Transformation of Research and Innovation). Supported by the Horizon 2020 'Science With and for Society' initiative, the goal of TRAIN is to pool the resources and expertise of the six founding partners in order to develop our Research and Innovation activities.

The outputs of TRAIN will fall primarily into three categories:

- Mapping and evaluation reports
- New tools to facilitate collaboration
- New strategic documents or policy recommendations

Some exciting work has already been done during the first year of this three-year project, especially with regard to the first bullet-point above. We now have a large amount of data about all six universities' innovation-related activities, including a general overview and more detailed insights into support structures and training provision. We are now reaching out to PhD students from different sectors in order to understand, more fully, their needs and experience of innovation within their institutions. This is the purpose of the following survey.

The key goal here is to look at ways to mainstream entrepreneurship in the mindset of students and to improve relations with external organisations (especially regional organisations) in a way that increases and enhances knowledge transfer. A further long-term aim is to make all EUTOPIA regions, and their innovation eco-systems, more accessible to each other, so that good practices can be shared and new opportunities identified.

The questions we would like to ask you fall into the following categories:

- Current awareness of and engagement with innovation training and provision at your institution.
- Current awareness of and engagement with mobility opportunities and reward structures surrounding innovation.
- Barriers and solutions to successful innovation.

Section 1

1.Name

Enter your answer

2.Which university are you primarily based in?

Univerza v Ljubljani

University of Warwick

Universitat Pompeu Fabra

CY Cergy Paris Université

Göteborgs Universitet

Vrije Universiteit Brussel

3.Course title Single line text.

Enter your answer

4.Sector (e.g. STEM, Arts etc.)

Enter your answer

5.Gender Multiple choice.

Male

Female

Non-binary

Other

Prefer not to say

Section 2

Innovation and You

6.Are you interested in innovation?

Yes

No

Maybe

7.Please elaborate on your interest in innovation:

Enter your answer

8.What does 'innovation' mean to you?

Enter your answer

9.Do you consider yourself to be innovative (or creative or entrepreneurial)?

1 = not very and 10 = very Rating.

1

2

3

4

5

6

7

8

9

10

10.Please elaborate on your previous answer

Enter your answer

11.Have you engaged with business or industry?

Yes

No

12.If yes, please include further information about these organisations

Enter your answer

13.If not, please indicate why not:

Enter your answer

Section 3

Innovation provision

14.Are you aware of opportunities to learn about innovation and entrepreneurship within your institution? (e.g. training programmes, mentoring, expert advice etc.)

Yes

No

15.If yes, please elaborate (provide name of service etc.):

Enter your answer

16.Have you undertaken any training related to innovation and entrepreneurship during your PhD?

Yes

No

17.If yes, was it helpful?

Yes

No

Partly/to some extent

18.Please elaborate further on your previous answer:

Enter your answer

19.If you have not undertaken any training, please indicate why:

Access or availability

Time

Interest

Other

20.If other, please elaborate further:

Enter your answer

21. Did you undertake any training related to innovation and entrepreneurship at bachelor or masters level?

Yes

No

22. If so, was it helpful? Please elaborate:

Enter your answer

23. If you did not undertake any training, please indicate why:

Access and availability

Time

Interest

Other

24. Please elaborate on your previous answer:

Enter your answer

25. Does the current innovation/entrepreneurship provision in your institution meet your needs?

Yes

No

Partly/to some extent

26. If yes, please specify which needs were met?

Enter your answer

27. If not, please indicate how it could be improved: Single line text.

Enter your answer

Section 4

Support Structures

28. Are you aware of the Innovation support structures within your institutions? (e.g. Tech Transfer Offices, Business Development Officers, Business office etc.) Single choice.

Yes

No

29. Have you accessed these services?

Yes

No

30. If not, please indicate why:

Availability

Time

Interest

Not had an idea that I wanted to pursue

There was no need

Other

31. If so, please elaborate on your experience:

Enter your answer

32. If other, please elaborate further:

Enter your answer

33. Do the support structures available meet your needs?

Yes

No

Partly/to some extent

34. If yes, please specify which needs were met:

Enter your answer

35. If not, please indicate how they could be improved:

Enter your answer

36. Are you aware of Innovation support structures outside your institution?

Yes

No

37. If yes, please specify below:

Enter your answer

Section 5

Mobility opportunities

38. Are you aware of mobility opportunities within your institution? .

Yes

No

39. If so, please specify which programmes:

Enter your answer

40. Have you participated in a mobility opportunity before?

Yes

No

41. If so, did it help you to develop innovation skills?

Yes

No

Partly/to some extent

42. Please elaborate on your previous answer:

Enter your answer

43. If you have not participated in a mobility opportunity, please indicate why:

Access and availability

Time

Interest

Other

44.If other, please elaborate further below:

Enter your answer

Section 6

Reward & Incentive Structures

45.Are there clear incentives and reward structures within your institution for engaging in innovative activity?

Yes

No

I do not know

46.If so, how have you benefited?

Enter your answer

47.If not, would a reward structure motivate you further to engage in innovative activity?

Yes

No

Maybe

48.What kind of rewards/incentives would motivate you further?

Enter your answer

Section 7

Barriers & Solutions to successful innovation

49.Have you experienced any of the following barriers to successful innovation:

Licencing across borders

International competition rules

Rules on company ownership

Other

50.If so, please indicate how these issues were addressed or solved:

Enter your answer

51.What sort of support would help you to overcome these barriers?

Enter your answer

52.Have you explored any of the following digital solutions to innovation?

Virtual meeting platforms

Blended networking

Virtual mobility

Other

53.If so, please explain what you have found helpful:

Enter your answer

54.If not, please explain why:

Enter your answer

Section 8

Innovation Focus Groups

Thank you for taking the time to complete this questionnaire. Once the results have been analysed we intend to hold follow-on focus groups/workshops around key emerging themes.

55.Please indicate whether you would be interested in participating in a follow-on focus group meeting or workshop?

Yes

No

56.If so, please include your email address below:

Enter your answer

8. Appendix 2: focus group questions

8.1. 'Implementers' focus group questions

If you have been a part of implementing such incentive initiatives...

Method:

E.g. why did you choose this/these incentive initiatives?

How did you fund it?

How did you spread it to potential users/recipients?

Result:

Did the info about the offer spread well, including to groups that would normally not engage in collaboration & innovation?

Did many apply / nominate for it?

Had they understood the scope, what it was for?

Did you feel it reached/gathered relevant 'users'/recipients?

Effect:

Did you see any change in behavior of the researchers (or PhD students) after the implementation of this initiative?

Did you see any change in culture, e.g. how the researchers (or PhD students) talk about collaboration & innovation?

Did you see any change in behaviour of or awareness from external actors?

What are the major benefits you see from it, for your e.g. institution or department?

What were effects you wished for that didn't happen? Why do you think that didn't happen?

Sustainability / applicability:

(How long) have you continued with the initiative? Do you/does the management think it's reasonable to keep funding?

(if applicable) Comparing different incentive initiatives, which do you prefer, and why?

(Which) do you think would be relevant to implement on a EUTOPIA level?

8.2. 'Recipients' focus group questions

If you have been a recipient of such an incentive initiative...

How did you hear about it?

Why did you feel it was relevant for you to apply / nominate for?

What did it help you achieve?

What could have made it even more relevant in your situation?

Have you received positive affirmation / acknowledgement for it? From whom? (e.g. colleagues, students, external actors, etc.)

Has it changed your view on engaging in collaboration & innovation?

What would you need to keep engaging in collaboration & innovation?